

IMPACT OF GREEN HRM IN JOB SATISFACTION: THE MEDIATING MECHANISM OF EMPLOYEES GREEN BEHAVIOR IN BANKING SECTORS AT KARACHI

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Abstract

This study attempts to investigate how green HRM practices impact employee well-being at work and how green behavior is implemented by employees in Pakistani banking sectors using green business planning and green human resource management (GHRM). To promote environmentally conscious behavior among employees and facilitate sustainable development, GHRM places a strong emphasis on job satisfaction. Primary information was acquired for the quantitative study of thirty-one banking employees in Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan, using a printed questionnaire. The sample size is 383 which is calculated by Surveysystem.com calculator's population size is three hundred thousand. The process of acquiring data involved the use of surveys and sampling as convenient methods. A cross-sectional survey approach was used in the study. Work satisfaction and green HRM practices have a favorable correlation, per this study. Furthermore, the outcomes support the hypothesis. Furthermore, the findings support the hypothesis that employee green behavior acts as a mediator between job satisfaction and green HRM practices. It is implied by the partial mediation that additional factors shaped the relationship. Creating a sustainable work culture is essential to increasing job satisfaction and staff dedication to the environment. Businesses should give employees the chance to engage in sustainable practices, promote open channels of communication for talking about environmental challenges, and reward collaboration and participation in sustainability initiatives.

Keywords: *Employees Green Behavior, Green HRM Practices, Job Satisfaction*

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the study

Green HR is a recently developed idea that is widely used in the human resource department these days to mobilize performance with the least amount of paper-based effort. This idea is contributing to the banking industry's rapid advancement while also improving our quality of life by reducing environmental pollution. Green HR practices aim to ensure that the green banking system is fully implemented in the HR department as well as in all banking operations. For this reason, people must adopt green behaviors in order to protect the environment, the planet, and humankind. Although greening employees from top to bottom is not an easy process, pro-environmental plans and the practical use of green human resource management (GHRM) techniques will result in a favorable outcome for the green environment (Bangwal & Tiwari, 2015).

By using Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) techniques can help businesses implement green business plans (Ali et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022). To encourage employees to operate in an environmentally responsible manner and support long-term success, GHRM works to integrate environmental sustainability concepts into various facets of human resource management. Programs teaching employees how to preserve the environment can be included in GHRM practices (Oubrich et al., 2021). By providing education on environmental issues and sustainability, businesses can assist their employees in realizing the significance of acting in an environmentally friendly manner. Educating staff members about the company's environmental objectives may encourage them to take steps toward achieving the goals (Farrukh et al., 2022).

1.2. Research Objectives

The primary focus of this research is on the role of Green HRM in mediating the relationship between job satisfaction and employee's green behavior. It specifically seeks to

- To measure the Green HRM to Job satisfaction
- To measure the Green HRM on Green Employees Behavior.
- To measure the Green HRM that mediates the relationship between Green HRM and Green employees Behavior.

1.3. Research Questions

RQ1:How do employees perceive the implementation of Green HRM practices in their workplace?

RQ2:How does employee perception of Green HRM practices relate to overall job satisfaction?

RQ3:How does green behavior among employees mediate the relationship between Green HRM practices and job satisfaction?

1.4. Significance of Study

The study is noteworthy because it addresses the growing importance of environmental sustainability and social responsibility in business operations. The banking sector in Pakistan is one of the country's largest and most influential, making it an ideal sector to investigate for the adoption of green HRM practices. The current paper aims to shed light on green HR practices in the banking sector of Pakistan. As a result, it allows stakeholders to gain meaningful insights into the implementation of GHRM practices. Furthermore, the proposed conceptual framework has practical implications for senior human resource professionals and managers in terms of leveraging their key role in environmentally friendly HR practices. Researchers can benefit from understanding the current state of GHRM practices while considering future green HR trends and study recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory is derived from social psychology and examines the exchange of obligations, resources, and advantages between individuals in intimate relationships (Jahan & Kim, 2020). According to this, people interact with one another with the hopes of learning something beneficial and avoiding something negative. These interactions are founded on reciprocity, which implies that when someone helps or treats them well, they feel obligated to respond favorably. The use of Social Exchange Theory in the workplace demonstrates that employees evaluate their own experiences based on the assistance and resources given by their managers, and that employees respond to this by giving work and contributions in return (Tsai & Kang, 2019; Yong et al., 2020). Employing Green HRM practices requires businesses to invest time and resources in encouraging sustainability and supporting employees who do environmentally friendly actions. Laws, incentive programs, training courses, and acknowledging environmentally friendly behavior are some examples of these approaches (Islam et al., 2020).

2.2. Green HRM and Job Satisfaction

Green HRM refers to the application of appropriate techniques and procedures for a sustainable environment in an organization's HRM goals and processes (Ali et al., 2020). These measures are intended to promote sustainability, reduce harm to the environment, and raise employee awareness of their responsibility to protect the environment. Nonetheless, an individual's assessment of their level of happiness at work is known as job satisfaction (Murtaza et al., 2021). Employee job satisfaction is higher when there is a sense of ownership and involvement in environmental projects (Jamal et al., 2021). Green HRM techniques can increase employees' commitment to the business and sense of purpose in their work. A company may be perceived by its employees as ethical and socially responsible if it demonstrates that it cares about sustainability and the environment. People

who can relate to the company's values and objectives at work may be happier there. Employee engagement can be increased through green human resource management practices that involve them in sustainable initiatives and decision-making (Ercantan & Eyupoglu, 2022). Employees experience a sense of purpose and fulfillment when they believe their work is making a positive impact on a larger cause. It is imperative to bear in mind that the impact of Green HRM practices on job satisfaction varies depending on the individual and the organization. The mindset of the company, employee attitudes toward Green HRM practices, and the extent to which they are implemented can all have an impact on the strength of the relationship (Alavi and Afghakhani, 2023).

H1 GHRM has positive relationship between Jobs satisfaction.

2.3. GHRM and Employees Green Behavior

Employee green behaviors should be anticipated because of GHRM for the reasons listed below. First, it is likely to increase employee green awareness and comprehension if the firm communicates its desire for being green during recruitment and takes into account each candidate's environmental beliefs during the employee selection process (Renwick et al., 2013). Second, getting staff members involved in green initiative execution and offering green training are probably going to improve staff members' capacities, knowledge, and abilities as well as increase their psychological openness to adopting green practices. Third, according to HRM theories, employees must recognize the necessity and urgency of implementing HRM practices if they are to be effective in promoting appropriate workplace behavior (Nishii, Lepak, & Schneider, 2008). Adopting GHRM practices and policies is likely to demonstrate an organization's commitment to preserving the environment, which is likely to motivate staff to strive toward the organization's green objectives. Finally, encouraging staff members to participate in and support green initiatives through promotions and awards that acknowledge and value their green performance encourages them to do so (Renwick et al., 2013). According to Dumont et al. (2017), who studied Chinese employees, GHRM had a direct and indirect impact on in-role green behaviors, but only indirectly on extra-role green behaviors through the development of psychological green climate. These findings support the points raised above. Saeed et al. (2019) conducted a recent study in which they attempted to illustrate the beneficial impact of GHRM practices on pro-environmental behaviors among employees in Pakistan across a broad range of businesses. Green behaviors may be expected to be directly influenced by GHRM practices because they are officially appreciated and rewarded and thus become customary workplace behavior. However, because voluntary green behavior is not officially recognized and decorated, it may or may not be directly influenced by GHRM practices; rather, it is influenced by individuals' awareness of an organization's green culture, their willingness to execute such behaviors, and the green habits that they follow in their daily lives (Dumont et al., 2017).

H2 GHRM has Positive Relationship between Employees Green Behavior.

2.4. Job Satisfaction

According to Spector (1997), job satisfaction, also known as employee satisfaction or job satisfaction, is a gauge of how happy employees are with their jobs, regardless of whether they enjoy their jobs overall or just certain parts of them, like the nature of the work or supervision. This job satisfaction measures how much workers enjoy themselves and how they feel about their work (Dayal & Verma, 2021). Giving staff members access to environmentally friendly resources, like recycling centers or energy-saving machinery, demonstrates to them that the business is making a concerted effort to reduce its environmental effect. Like this, involving staff in environmental decision-making processes conveys that their opinions and contributions are valued in shaping the company's sustainability objectives (Ababneh 2021). Examples of this kind of engagement include asking for suggestions for sustainable projects or creating green team-term relationship between standard GHRM practices and the behavioral effects on employees. These were mediated by attitudinal variables, which pertain to a person's cognitive, affective, and activation dimensions. Similarly, GHRM has promoted the development and investigation of novel settings were illustrate the implicit social and mental processes that connect GHRM procedures to workers' GB (Renwick, Redman, and Maguire 2013; Dumont, Shen, and Deng 2017).

H3. GHRM mediates the relationship between Employees Green Behavior and Job Satisfaction.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Theoretical Framework

A conceptual framework based on the Social Exchange Theory can be applied to understand and analyze various social relationships, including those within organizations and between employees and employers. The Social Exchange Theory posits that individuals engage in social interactions and relationships with the expectation of mutual benefit and reciprocity. Here is a conceptual framework using the Social Exchange Theory as applied to the context of employee-employed relationships within an organization.

Figure-1 Framework Model

3.2. Research Design

Cooper and Schindler (2006) state that specific behavior taking place in each context can be measured using descriptive study. Therefore, it is thought that the best method for this study is to employ a quantitative descriptive technique with Likert-scale questions. In this instance, the research aims to quantify and examine the impact of green human resource management on firm performance. Respondent data has been gathered using an approved questionnaire. The study's population comprises all banks. Questionnaires will be used to gather data, and version 24.0 of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) used for analysis. A survey questionnaire was used to perform this investigation. The primary research approach was clear-cut and easy to understand. The quantitative approach, which took the shape of a questionnaire completed by the primary target population or respondents, and the qualitative method of literature review served as the foundation for the data collection.

3.3. Research Approach

This research employs an inductive methodology by gathering quantitative data and defining the relationship between variables through data analysis and theory.

3.4. Sampling Technique

There are two basic categories of sampling techniques: non-probability and probability.

The research employed a non-probability judgment sampling technique, whereby a random sample of people was picked based on their job positions and rankings within the banking sectors. Due to time constraints, 383 replies in total were administered in my study.

3.5. Target Population

The information was gathered from banking industry personnel, including managers, directors, assistant managers, HR officers, entry-level workers, and operational managers. The target audience was made up of people from across Karachi. The population size is two hundred thousand.

3.6. Sample Size

The goal of the study is to generate a population parameter estimate that is accurate to a predetermined degree (5% margin of error) and confidence (95% confidence level). This approach finds a middle ground between the practical implications of data collection and the required precision. The sample size was determined by measuring the various sample sizes that were employed in earlier research on green HR. As a result, 383 respondents were chosen as the sample size for this investigation. It is calculated by surveysystem.com calculator.

The image shows a web-based calculator titled "Determine Sample Size". It has a light gray background and a dark border. The interface includes the following elements:

- Confidence Level:** Two radio buttons are present, with "95%" selected and "99%" unselected.
- Confidence Interval:** A text input field containing the number "5".
- Population:** A text input field containing the number "200000".
- Buttons:** Two rounded rectangular buttons labeled "Calculate" and "Clear".
- Result:** A text input field at the bottom labeled "Sample size needed:" containing the number "383".

3.7. Data Collection

The survey research strategy was utilized to obtain data from my intended group using a questionnaire. Employees who were implementing Green HRM practices at their organization were given surveys to complete to get data from the intended audience.

In my research study, structured inquiries, an online survey questionnaire, and Google Form were utilized to administer additional data collection. These methods are dependable and often expedient in today's world. To obtain quick answers, the survey questionnaire was emailed to the relevant department, business representatives, and the intended audience directly.

3.8. Instrumentation

The respondents' name, age, gender, salary, and experience were among the personal details included in the questionnaire's blank sections. The purpose of gathering the background data is to use it for descriptive statistics during the analysis stage. The following section of the questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale, with one denoting Strongly Disagree and five denoting Strongly Agree, to ask questions concerning several research aspects. Each of the five options that the participants thought was the best might be chosen. There were closed-ended questions on the survey, and each question had three variables which are green HRM, Job satisfaction, green employee's behavior extracted from Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017) which is comprised of six chastisements to measure. Job satisfaction extracted from Jamal, M.T et al,2021 which consists of five statements to measure. Green employees' behavior extracted from Rubel, M. R. B., Kee, D. M. H., & Rimi, N. N. (2021) which contains six statements to measure. And we get data from banking sectors such as NBP, BOP, Meezan, Allied bank, Askari, Faisal bank, Punjab bank, Sindh bank, Habib Metro.

Table 3.1: Data collection instrumentation

Variable Name	N Items	Likert Type	Source(s)
GHRM	6	5-Point	Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017)
Job Satisfaction	5	5-Point	Jamal, M.T et al,2021
Green Employees Behavior	6	5-Point	M. R. B., Kee, D. M. H., & Rimi, N. N. (2021)

3.9. Ethical Consideration

As the study's researcher, it was my duty to ensure that study participants would not be in danger. Prior to the poll, the consent of the respondents was acquired. I assume full responsibility for safeguarding study participants' confidential information. Data storage will not be lost. All communications pertaining to the research project shall be open and truthful. Any sort of data misrepresentation, including discriminatory misrepresentation, will be avoided.

3.10. Statistical Technique

The statistical package for social science, or SPSS, is used in this study to examine the descriptive statistics and demographics. Additionally, the estimate measurement model and the structural model (PLS-SEM) were both created using partial least squares structural equation modeling. Investigating the legitimacy and dependability of the single item level is the main goal of maintaining an estimate model in the PLS-SEM.

4.Data Analysis

4.1. Overall Reliability Test

Table 1

Reliability Test(n=383)

Reliability Statistics		
	Cronbach's	
	Alpha	Based
		on
Cronbach's	Standardized	
Alpha	Items	N of Items
.827	.876	26

Cuieford (1957) states that Cronbach's value of more than 0.7 indicates good reliability when measuring a variable, like a researcher (0.827) excellent reliability across all items.

4.2 Demographics Analysis

Table 4.2: Demographic Profile (n=383)

Banking Sector			
		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	224	58.5
	Female	159	41.5
Education	Undergraduate	24	6.3
	Graduate	139	36.3
	Masters	220	57.4
Age	20-30	189	49.3
	30-40	139	36.3
	40-50	32	8.4
	50 Above	23	6.0
Job Position	Supervisor	100	26.1
	Assistant Manager	136	35.5
	Managerial	132	34.5
	Director	15	3.9
Experience	1-5	156	40.7
	6-10	128	33.4
	11-20	70	18.3
	20 Above	29	7.6

Table 4.2 Summarizes the demographics profile of the respondents. The total number of valid responses is 383, out of 224(58.5%) male and 159 (41.5%) females. The qualifications in which twenty-four are undergraduate, while 139 (36.3%) are graduated and

220 57.4 are masters. The respondents who were between 20-30 ages are 189 49.3,139 36.3 in between 30-40 ages. Where respondents age in between 40-50 are 32(8.4%) and other 50 above are 23(6.0%).The job position are supervisor 100(26.1%).Assistant manager are 136(35.5%) and managerial are 132(34.5%) and Directors are 15(3.9%).The above table shows the work experience between 1-5 year is 156(40.7%) ,128(33.4%) have work experience between 6-10 year.70(18.3%) have work experience between 11-20 year.29(7.6%) have work experience between 20 above.

4.3. Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
GHRM	21.0100	5.47076	29.929
JS	18.6162	3.42472	11.729
GEB	23.2245	4.48027	20.073

The above table shows the mean and score of respondents which are Green HRM (M=21.0100,SD=5.47076,V=29.929),JobSatisfaction(M=18.6162,SD=3.42472,V=11.729),green

employees behavior (M=23.3345,SD=4.48027,V=20.073)In the table above the highest value of mean is Green employees behavior (23.2245) and lowest of Job Satisfaction is (18.6162).The highest value of Standard Deviation is GHRM (5.47076) and lowest value is Job Satisfaction.(3.42472).The Highest value of variance is GHRM (29.929) and the lowest value is Job Satisfaction (11.729).

4.4. Hypothesis Testing by using Path analysis.

The following table 4.4 shows the results of hypothesis testing using PLS bootstrapping at a suggested five thousand subsamples, two-tailed estimates, and a 5% probability level.

Table 4.4.1

Hypothesis Testing by using Path analysis.

Variable	Original sample (O)	Sample means (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	Decision
GEB -> JS	0.332	0.341	0.067	4.938	0.000	Accepted
GHRM -> GEB	0.492	0.495	0.043	11.367	0.000	Accepted
GHRM -> JS	0.295	0.291	0.069	4.301	0.000	Accepted

Above table has shown that G has a positively GEB significant effect on JS ($\beta = 0.332$; $p < 0.000$) accepting hypothesis-1, GHRM significant effect on GEB ($\beta = 0.492$; $p < 0.000$) accepting hypothesis-2 and GHRM significant effects on JS ($\beta = 0.295$; $p < 0.000$) accepting hypothesis.

Figure 4.1

PLS Bootstrapping Illustration

5. Conclusion

The study on the impact of green HRM practices on work satisfaction. This study provides insights into how firms might promote sustainable behaviors and increase employee satisfaction. The study highlights the importance of employees' commitment to environmental sustainability. Research indicates that employees who priorities environmental responsibility are more satisfied with their careers. Green HRM practice helps workers through their "green behavior," which demonstrates their motivation, willingness, and involvement in environmentally friendly practices. This promise provides employees with a sense of purpose, fulfilment, and unity in the company's environmental initiatives, leading to increased job satisfaction. The findings highlight the significance of implementing sustainable HR practices and engaging employees in green initiatives. Using these strategies, organizations may create a more ecologically friendly workplace, leading to happy employees by green behavior. Employees prefer organizations that priorities green HRM practices. Green practices lead to elevated levels of employee engagement and dedication. Regularly assessing the possible impact of GHRM practices on HRM issues is crucial due to their complicated nature. When opting to go sustainable, HR managers

should first identify the extent and complexity of green practices in their organization. This will help the firm express its green-related aims and vision.

Effective human resource operations, including recruiting, training, and development, are vital for a company's environmental performance. Green HRM methods are vital for attracting and retaining green personnel that exhibit creative behaviors and attitudes. Individuals with green skills are essential for developing and maintaining environmentally friendly efficiency within a team. Human resources professionals develop programmes and initiatives to promote green skills among employees. HR may motivate employees by providing green rewards that are linked to their success. Designed programmes teach the importance of developing green skills and implementing them consistently. The banking sector is the backbone of all other financial activities and is essential to the growth of the Pakistani economy, it has become increasingly popular. A sizable portion of the service sector is the banking business, which has obligations to its clients for high-quality services, workers for a safe workplace, and social responsibility. Banks have realized that going green and incorporating green practices into everyday operations is beneficial since it makes employees happier. Most scheduled banks are concentrating on this and trying to draw and retain their best employees by using Green HRM practices since these give them a competitive edge so the conclusion is that green human resource management has a positive relationship between green behavior and Job satisfaction and green employees behavior have positive relationship between Green Human resource management.

5.1. Future Recommendations

In the modern world, human resources are just as valuable as material wealth, advanced technology, etc. Organizations must therefore take human resources into account because they are crucial to their improvement. Furthermore, the study's findings indicate that improved hiring and selection practices, performance reviews, and compensation are more significant variables that influence how satisfied employees are with their jobs at the company. They ought to concentrate on making them better. Organizations are developing new plans and policies to meet these main goals. The process for creating and overseeing talent management is under the purview of human resource functions. Every firm needs to prioritize employee satisfaction. Employers should give employees' needs their whole attention and concentrate on meeting their needs.

It is suggested that a comprehensive approach be used when integrating Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) techniques in the banking industry to improve employee satisfaction. This entails providing staff members with ongoing education and training in innovative technologies and sustainable banking practices. Increased job satisfaction and environmental sustainability can be achieved through implementing innovative technologies, flexible work schedules, and extensive employee engagement initiatives.

Employee sense of purpose is enhanced by inclusive decision-making, well-being programs, and transparent communication on sustainability objectives. Furthermore, by including green performance metrics in assessments and cultivating alliances with environmental groups, the bank can maintain its competitiveness, social responsibility, and appeal as an employer while also keeping up with changing employee demands concerning environmental responsibility.

In the future, research on the relationship between Green HRM practices, employee green behavior to being green, and work satisfaction could be conducted using a continuous approach. Determining the cause of these changes and how they might occur would be simpler. Finally, to gather first-hand data for the study, polls were employed. Future research could employ a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative discussions or focus groups.

Gaining more insight into employees' knowledge, attitudes, and experiences regarding green HRM practices, green commitment, and job satisfaction would be aided by this. Qualitative data may aid in our comprehension of the underlying mechanisms and contextual elements influencing these relationships.

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